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Farmers' Perception and Adaptation to Climate Change in Kibangay, Bukidnon

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Abstract

This study examined the perception and adaptation strategies of farmers towards the impacts of climate change in Kibangay, Lantapan, Bukidnon. Specifically, it aimed to analyze the farmers' demographic profile in terms of age, sex, monthly income, and educational attainment; assess their perception and experiences regarding climate change; and identify their adaptation strategies. The study also tested for significant differences in farmers' perception and experience when grouped by demographic profile. Using a purposive sampling method, data were collected from 100 respondents through questionnaires. Results revealed that 41% of the farmers were middle-aged (46–60 years old), 81% were men, 66% were elementary graduates, and 84% had a monthly income ranging from ₱5,000 to ₱15,000. Farmers generally agreed on their perceptions of climate change and its impacts, identifying obstacles such as weather unpredictability and resource limitations. The most commonly adopted adaptation strategy was crop rotation, with 63% of respondents practicing it, followed by intercropping (52%) and adjusting planting schedules (47%). Statistical analysis showed significant differences in perceptions and experiences based on educational attainment ($p < 0.05$), suggesting that farmers with higher education levels had a more informed understanding of climate change. This underscores the importance of education in enhancing farmers' climate resilience and adaptation strategies. The study addresses a gap in understanding how demographic factors shape climate change adaptation among small-scale farmers, highlighting the need for targeted educational programs to improve adaptive capacity.

Keywords: *perception, adaptation strategies, climate change, farmer*

Introduction

Increased global temperatures and extreme weather phenomena such as heat waves, droughts, floods, and storms serve as evidence of climate change. These events impact the economy, environment, and communities. The Philippines is particularly vulnerable due to its geographical position, tropical Pacific archipelagic structure, and demographic distribution. In recent years, people have already experienced the adverse effects of climate change, which is anticipated to exacerbate the nation's medium- to long-term issues if both local and international measures are not implemented (NCCAP 2011–2028).

To address the global climate crisis, the Philippine government enacted the Climate Change Act (Republic Act 9729), which provides a policy framework to systematically tackle the escalating dangers to community well-being and environmental sustainability. This legislation established the Climate Change Commission, tasked with formulating strategic frameworks and programs, integrating climate risk mitigation into national and local development plans, providing policy recommendations, and investing in climate-sensitive sectors (NCCAP 2011–2028).

Climate change is a major obstacle to achieving global sustainable development goals, particularly in rural areas where it has negatively affected food security and public health. Previous studies provide substantial evidence that climate change continues to adversely affect individuals and economies worldwide (Wang et al., 2020). Arouri et al. (2015) assert that climate change exacerbates natural disasters, altering the frequency, magnitude, duration, and timing of extreme weather events. As a result, decreased crop yields and agricultural productivity lead to food insecurity and increased impoverishment among farmers. Similarly, Ali and Erenstein (2017) highlight that climate change disproportionately impacts farmers and underprivileged populations in developing countries. In Southeast Asia, Pulhin et al. (2016) analyzed the adverse effects of climate change on agriculture, revealing that fluctuations in temperature and precipitation have contributed to heightened pest populations, soil erosion, degradation, and water stress. These factors have collectively resulted in a significant decrease in agricultural productivity, threatening food security. Among the most vulnerable groups are upland farmers, who rely heavily on rainfall for agriculture and have limited financial and technological resources to adapt to climate change. Nearly 26 million individuals inhabit the Philippine uplands and face these challenges daily.

In the Philippines, agriculture remains a primary livelihood, with rural farming communities particularly at risk from climate change impacts. Nearly 90% of households in Barangay Kibangay, Lantapan, Bukidnon, depend on agriculture for their livelihood (Municipality of Lantapan, 2015). This upland community is located within the critically endangered Panambongol and Tugasan watersheds, making local farming practices significant not only for the immediate population but also for those downstream. However, Kibangay farmers face numerous challenges, including resource deficiencies, limited technological access, and inadequate awareness of climate change adaptation strategies. Despite Kibangay's importance as a major vegetable-producing barangay in Mindanao, limited studies have explored the farmers' perceptions of climate change and their adaptive responses. Understanding their perceptions and adaptation strategies is crucial for developing effective, localized climate adaptation measures.

To address these concerns, this study aims to investigate the perceptions and adaptation strategies of farmers in Kibangay, Lantapan, Bukidnon, in response to climate change. Specifically, it seeks to analyze the demographic characteristics of farmers in terms of age,

sex, monthly income, and educational attainment; assess their perceptions and experiences regarding climate change; and identify the adaptation strategies they employ. Additionally, the study examines whether significant differences exist in farmers' perceptions and experiences based on demographic characteristics.

The findings of this study are expected to benefit Xavier de Kibangay High School, policymakers, planners, farmers, consumers, and future researchers. By providing insights into local farmers' climate change perceptions and adaptation strategies, this research can guide the development of more effective climate change adaptation policies and programs for the agricultural sector.

Methodology

This study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design to explore farmers' perceptions and adaptation strategies to climate change. This design was appropriate for assessing relationships between variables without manipulation. Surveys served as the primary data collection method, allowing for a comprehensive analysis of farmers' experiences and adaptation measures.

The research was conducted in Kibangay, a hilly and progressive barrio in Lantapan, Bukidnon, which comprises 10 sitios: Bulanga, Calamba, Centro Kibangay, Kibuda, Kimanga, Maliwanag, Nakadulog, Old Kibangay, Taguisihan, and Tumpagan. Using a purposive sampling method, 100 respondents were selected, with 10 respondents equally distributed across each sitio. Barangay officials and sitio leaders assisted in identifying respondents to ensure fairness and minimize geographical bias.

Primary data were collected using a survey questionnaire composed of closed-ended questions designed to align with the research objectives. The questionnaire, adapted from Binaya, G. (2021), was translated into Cebuano to enhance clarity and response accuracy, facilitating a more precise understanding of farmers' perceptions.

For data analysis, descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations were used to summarize demographic characteristics and response trends. Inferential statistical tests, including chi-square tests and t-tests, were conducted to determine significant differences in perceptions and adaptation strategies based on demographic factors. The data were processed using SPSS, with a significance level set at $p < 0.05$ to ensure the validity of findings.

Ethical considerations were strictly observed throughout the study. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring that they voluntarily agreed to participate with full awareness of the study's purpose and procedures. Confidentiality was maintained by anonymizing responses and restricting data access to authorized researchers only. These measures ensured the ethical integrity and credibility of the research.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents by Sitio*

<i>Name of Sitios</i>	<i>Number of Respondents</i>
Bulanga	10
Calamba	10
Centro Kibangay	10
Kibuda	10
Kimanga	10
Maliwanag	10
Nakadulog	10
Old Kibangay	10
Taguisihan	10
Tumpagan	10
Total	100

The data in Table 1 provides the distribution of respondents across ten sitios, with each sitio contributing an equal number of respondents to the total sample. Each sitio, from Bulanga to Tumpagan, had 10 respondents, indicating a uniform sampling approach. This equal distribution ensures that each sitio has equal representation in the study, minimizing potential biases related to the geographical location of the respondents. The total number of respondents across all sitios is 100, demonstrating a balanced and systematic sampling method. The data suggests that the study aimed to achieve fairness and consistency by allocating the same number of respondents to each sitio, regardless of population size or other factors. This approach is suitable when the goal is to compare responses equally across various areas.

Table 2. *Demographic profile of the farmers in terms of age*

<i>Age</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
15 – 30 Years Old	9	9.0
31 – 45 Years Old	39	39.0
46 – 60 Years Old	41	41.0
61 – 75 Years Old	11	11.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 2 shows the demographic profile of farmers based on age shows that the majority are within the middle-aged to older working groups. Farmers aged 46 to 60 years old make up the largest portion, accounting for 41% of the total, indicating that this age group is the most dominant in farming activities. Close behind, farmers aged 31 to 45 years old represent 39% of the population, suggesting that middle-aged individuals also play a significant role in farming. In contrast, younger farmers, those aged 15 to 30, only make up 9% of the total, highlighting a smaller involvement of youth in farming. Meanwhile, the 61 to 75-year-old group comprises 11%, showing that some senior citizens remain engaged in agricultural work. Overall, 80% of the farmers fall between the ages of 31 and 60, reflecting that farming is predominantly carried out by middle-aged and older adults, with fewer young and elderly participants.

The findings of the study were corroborated by the research conducted by M.N. Uddin et al. (2017). Determinants influencing farmers' adaptation techniques to environmental degradation and the impacts of climate change: A farm-level survey in Bangladesh indicates that the average age of respondents was approximately 43 years, comprising 71% of the age demographic, revealing that most farmers in the region are youthful to middle-aged.

Table 3. *Demographic profile of the farmers in terms of sex*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Male	81	81.0
Female	19	19.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 3 reveals the demographic profile of farmers in terms of sex. There is significant gender disparity, with the majority being male. Out of the total, 81% of the farmers are men, indicating that farming is predominantly a male-dominated activity in this community. In contrast, women account for only 19% of the farmers, suggesting that their involvement in farming is relatively limited. This gender imbalance highlights the male predominance in agricultural work, with only a small proportion of female farmers actively engaged in the sector.

The findings of the study were corroborated by the research conducted by Aliyu Shu'aibu Muhammad et al. (2020) on the Effects of Demographic Characteristics on Farmers' Responses to Climate Change in Bunkure, Nigeria. The gender distribution of respondents in the survey indicated that female farmers constituted merely 5% of the sample, whilst male respondents comprised 95%. The results demonstrate that men constitute the predominant demographic of farmers in the region.

Table 4. *Demographic profile of the farmers in terms of educational attainment*

<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
No Grade Completed	6	6.0
Elementary Graduate	66	66.0
High School Graduate	20	20.0
College Graduate	8	8.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 4 presents the demographic profile of farmers based on their educational attainment. The majority of the farmers, 66%, are elementary graduates, indicating that most have received some level of basic education. High school graduates make up 20% of the group, suggesting that a smaller proportion has completed secondary education. Only 8% of the farmers have attained a college degree, reflecting a limited access to or pursuit of higher education within this population. Notably, 6% of the farmers have no formal education.

The study's findings were corroborated by the research conducted by M.N. Uddin et al. (2017) on the factors influencing farmers' adaptation methods to environmental degradation and climate change impacts: A farm-level analysis in Bangladesh. Data indicates that over fifty percent of respondents (52%) have attained their basic level of schooling.

Table 5. *Demographic profile of the farmers in terms of monthly income*

<i>Monthly Income</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
5,000.00 – 15,000.00	84	84.0
15,001 – 25,000.00	4	4.0
25,001 – 35,000.00	8	8.0
Above 35,000.00	4	4.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 5 illustrates the demographic profile of farmers based on their monthly income. The majority, or 84%, of the farmers earn between ₱5,000 and ₱15,000 per month, indicating that most of them have relatively low-income levels. A smaller portion, 8%, earns between ₱25,001 and ₱35,000, while only 4% of the farmers fall into both the ₱15,001 to ₱25,000 and above ₱35,000 income brackets. These figures suggest that the majority of farmers have limited earnings, with only a few achieving higher income levels. This income distribution reflects a generally low-income profile within the farming community.

The findings of the study were corroborated by the research conducted by M.N. Uddin et al. (2017) on the factors influencing farmers' adaptation strategies to environmental degradation and the impacts of climate change: A farm-level analysis in Bangladesh Climate. The data indicates that the predominant monthly income, including 73%, is between the range of 5,001-10,000.00, and the remaining 27% represents other income brackets.

Table 6. *Perception and experience to climate change*

Indicator	Mean	SD	Qualitative Interpretation
Too much heavy rain (Subra nga ulan)	3.67	0.620	Agree
Extremes in temperature (Taas ang temperature)	3.57	0.868	Agree
Drought, Long dry spells during the season (Nakasinati ug taas nga hulaw o ting-init)	3.57	0.795	Agree
The rains start late and end early (Dali pag-undang sa ulan)	3.37	0.939	Neutral
The rain is more Erratic (Dili regular ang pag-ulan)	3.33	1.006	Neutral
Overall	3.50	0.605	Agree

Scale: 4.20–5.00 (Strongly Agree) | 3.40–4.19 (Agree) | 2.60–3.39 (Neutral) | 1.80–2.59 (Disagree) | 1.00–1.79 (Strongly Disagree)

Table 6 presents the perceptions and experiences of farmers regarding climate change, with various indicators measured on a scale from 1 to 5. The overall mean perception score is 3.50 (SD = 0.605), which falls within the "Agree" range, indicating that farmers generally acknowledge the impact of climate change in their experiences.

Among the indicators, "Too much heavy rain" has the highest mean score of 3.67 (SD = 0.620), suggesting that farmers frequently observe excessive rainfall in their environment. This perception could imply that farmers are particularly concerned about the effects of heavy rainfall, such as flooding and its impact on crop yields. On the other hand, the indicators with the lowest mean scores are "The rain is more erratic" and "The rains start late and end early," with mean scores of 3.33 (SD = 1.006) and 3.37 (SD = 0.939), respectively.

Overall, these findings highlight that farmers are becoming increasingly aware of the effects of climate change, particularly the intensity of rainfall, which can directly influence agricultural productivity and necessitate adaptations in farming practices.

The findings of this study were corroborated by Ochieng's (2016) research, which utilized Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) in Southern Africa and determined that qualitative analyses of farmers' perceptions of rainfall enhance conventional meteorological statistics with valuable information. Climate records indicated that the notion of increased variability in rainfall had emerged. The research indicate that this phenomenon occurs because weather events affecting farmers' livelihoods, particularly over successive seasons, are more vividly recalled than those that do not harm their livelihoods.

Akanbi et al. (2021) assert that extreme weather occurrences, including heat waves, storms, droughts, floods, and soil degradation, render agricultural productivity increasingly uncertain. Climate change affects crop output variably throughout different regions. Food security is jeopardized by these changes, especially in regions where rain-fed crops constitute the main source of staple food.

The perspectives of farmers are crucial for understanding the impacts of climate change, as they are often the first to detect alterations in weather patterns. Research indicates that numerous farmers observe alterations in the frequency and intensity of precipitation, especially those experiencing substantial rainfall.

Table 7. *Impact of climate change*

Indicator	Mean	SD	Qualitative Interpretation
Increase in Pests and Diseases (Pagdaghan sa dangan, peste o sakit)	3.64	0.612	Agree
Reduction in Crops Production (Pagamay o Pagkunuhod sa abot sa yuta)	3.42	0.755	Agree
Land degradation (Pagkawala sa tambok sa yuta)	3.41	0.753	Agree
Biodiversity loss (Pagkadaut sa kinaiyahan)	3.19	0.706	Neutral
Shortage of Food (Kakulangan sa pagkaon)	3.10	0.689	Neutral
Overall	3.35	0.520	Agree

Scale: 4.20–5.00 (Strongly Agree) | 3.40–4.19 (Agree) | 2.60–3.39 (Neutral) | 1.80–2.59 (Disagree) | 1.00–1.79 (Strongly Disagree)

Table 7 detailing the impact of climate change on agriculture reveals several key indicators measured on a scale of 1 to 5. The overall mean score for the perceptions of climate change impact is 3.35 (SD = 0.520), indicating a general agreement among respondents regarding the negative effects of climate change.

The indicator with the highest mean score is "Increase in Pests and Diseases" (Mean = 3.64, SD = 0.612), suggesting that farmers strongly recognize the rise in pest and disease occurrences as a significant consequence of climate change. This perception implies a critical concern for farmers, as an increase in pests and diseases can lead to further reductions in crop yields and, consequently, food security.

Conversely, the indicator with the lowest mean score is "Shortage of Food" (Mean = 3.10, SD = 0.689). This lower mean suggests that while farmers acknowledge the impact of climate change, they perceive food shortages as a somewhat less frequent or severe issue compared to the increase in pests and diseases.

In conclusion, although farmers are typically cognizant of the detrimental impacts of climate change, especially for pest and disease

control, they may not perceive food shortages as closely associated with climate change.

The research conducted by Abid et al. (2016) corroborated the results of the study. The vulnerability, adaptation, and risk perceptions related to climate change are analyzed at the agricultural level in Punjab, Pakistan. The findings indicate that farmers most commonly observe production fluctuations, pest and disease infestations, and alterations in farming processes affecting their crops.

Farmers report a decline in crop productivity and an increase in crop failures. Many farmers have observed that significant variations in rainfall and temperature have resulted in a rise in pest and disease infestations. Farmers have perceived climate variability as a factor influencing alterations in the growing and sowing seasons.

The influence of climate change on disease and insect outbreaks is a critical concern that necessitates consideration.

Agriculturists must adjust to these shifting conditions by devising innovative pest control strategies, advocating for climate-resilient agriculture, and allocating resources for research to comprehend the changing dynamics of diseases and pests. If this issue is not addressed, agricultural output may continue to diminish, thereby jeopardizing food security.

Table 8. *Barriers Towards Farming Adaptation*

Indicator	Mean	SD	Qualitative Interpretation
Lack of technology (Kakulangan sa Teknolohiya)	3.19	0.775	Neutral
Lack of access to weather information (Kakulangan sa impormasyon sa klima)	3.18	0.770	Neutral
Lack of human resources (Kakulangan sa tawhanon nga kahinguhaan)	3.11	0.852	Neutral
Lack of government support Kakulangan sa supporta sa Gobyerno)	3.11	0.942	Neutral
Lack of knowledge and awareness (Kakulangan sa kahibalo)	2.96	0.864	Neutral
Overall	3.11	0.612	Neutral

Scale: 4.20–5.00 (Strongly Agree) | 3.40–4.19 (Agree) | 2.60–3.39 (Neutral) | 1.80–2.59 (Disagree) | 1.00–1.79 (Strongly Disagree)

Table 8 outlines the barriers towards farming adaptation, providing insights into various factors that farmers perceive as obstacles. The overall mean score for these barriers is 3.11 (SD = 0.612), indicating a neutral perception among farmers regarding the challenges they face in adapting their farming practices.

The indicator with the highest mean score is “Lack of technology” (Mean = 3.19, SD = 0.775), suggesting that farmers recognize insufficient technological resources as a notable barrier to adapting to changing conditions. This perception highlights the need for improved access to modern agricultural technologies, which could enhance productivity and resilience in the face of climate change.

Conversely, the indicator with the lowest mean score is “Lack of knowledge and awareness” (Mean = 2.96, SD = 0.864). This lower mean indicates that while farmers acknowledge the importance of knowledge and awareness for adaptation, they perceive this barrier as slightly less significant compared to the others.

In conclusion, although farmers recognize multiple barriers to adaptation as neutral in effect, the perceived absence of technology emerges as the most substantial obstacle.

The study's findings were corroborated by Adeoti et al. (2016) in their work titled "Farmers' Vulnerability, Perception, and Adaptation to Climate Change in Kwara State," utilizing the MNL model. The econometric analysis revealed that the most pertinent and important variables influencing farmers' selection of climate change adaptation strategies in the study area were temperature, rainfall, land ownership, farming experience, and the education level of the household head. The principal obstacles to adaptation encompass credit accessibility, land tenure challenges, and insufficient knowledge, information, and technology regarding adaptation solutions.

Furthermore, Abid et al. (2015) conducted a study in Pakistan's Punjab region about farmers' attitudes and plans for climate change adaptation, along with the influencing factors. The principal adaptation tactics employed by farmers in the study area were modifying crop varieties, revising planting schedules, including shade trees, and tweaking nutrient applications. The findings revealed that adaptation to climate change is impeded by various issues, including insufficient information, inadequate technology, resource limitations, and a scarcity of irrigation water in the research region.

The research underscores the pressing necessity for action, particularly in the domain of technology. A comprehensive plan is essential, as the absence of technology is a significant impediment intertwined with other factors. To facilitate farmers' adaptation to evolving conditions and ensure sustainable agricultural practices, it is essential to examine the complex interrelations among weather access, resources, knowledge, and contextual limitations. We can establish a more resilient and sustainable agricultural future by adopting a holistic strategy for farmer empowerment, promoting agricultural technology, and eliminating barriers to farming flexibility.

Table 9 presents the adaptation strategies employed by farmers in response to climate change, highlighting their frequency of use. The data indicates a strong reliance on several proactive measures to mitigate the impacts of climate variability.

The most commonly adopted strategy is “Practicing crop rotation”, with 99% of farmers implementing this approach. This high percentage suggests that farmers recognize the benefits of diversifying their crops to improve soil health and reduce pest pressures. Following closely is the strategy of “Adjusting planting time,” utilized by 98% of farmers. This indicates a proactive approach to align

planting schedules with changing weather patterns, reflecting an awareness of how timing can affect crop yields.

Table 9. *Adaptation Strategies to Climate Change*

<i>Adaptation Strategy</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Adjusting planting time (Pag-adjust sa panahon sa pagtanom)	98	98.0
Using crop varieties which is drought-tolerant (Mogamit ug tanom nga makasugakod Sa init)	93	93.0
Practicing crop rotation (Pagtanom ug lahi-lahi nga tanom)	99	99.0
Using organic fertilizers (Pagamit ug organikong abono)	87	87.0
Using water pump or irrigation (Pagamit ug puso o iregasyon)	44	44.0

Additionally, “Using crop varieties that are drought-tolerant” is employed by 93% of farmers, demonstrating a clear understanding of the need to select crops that can withstand climatic stress. In contrast, the use of “Organic fertilizers” is adopted by 87% of farmers, suggesting a preference for sustainable farming practices that enhance soil fertility without relying on synthetic inputs.

However, only 44% of farmers use “Water pumps or irrigation” systems, indicating a significant gap in irrigation practices. This low adoption rate could reflect limited access to necessary resources or infrastructure, which may hinder their ability to manage water effectively during periods of drought.

The findings of this study were corroborated by Gadédjisso-Tossou (2015), who examined the Maritime, Plateau, and Savannah Regions of Togo. He examined data from a cross-sectional survey employing descriptive statistics and mean difference learning (MNL). Farmers employed measures of adaptation such as crop diversification, crop rotation, seeking off-farm jobs, modifying land area, revising planting dates, and utilizing short-season varieties.

Furthermore, the research conducted by Kichamu et al. (2018) in the Mattungulu Sub-County of Eastern Kenya, Wamalwa et al. (2016) across three Sub-counties in Kisii County, Ochieng et al. (2017) in diverse agro-ecological zones in Kenya, and Mburu et al. (2015) in Yatta District, Kenya, indicated that the primary adaptation strategies employed by farmers were suitable. Alterations in crop varieties, planting schedules, crop diversification, and soil and water conservation methods were identified as the predominant strategies for adapting to climate change. Unreported findings from other studies revealed that more than fifty percent of respondents employed crop rotation as a coping strategy. In response to climate change, they implemented this measure to enhance their income and improve their standard of living.

Agriculturalists were increasingly cognizant of the impacts of climate change on their farming practices. The optimal adaptation strategy may vary according to geographic location and specific climatic challenges; nonetheless, crop rotation is broadly recognized as an effective and prevalent technique for mitigating the effects of climate change on agriculture. This method has numerous benefits for mitigating the effects of climate change. Crop rotation is advantageous for protecting the soil from erosion due to wind and heavy rainfall.

Table 10. *Test of significant difference on the farmers' perception and experience towards climate change when they are grouped according to the farmers' demographic profile*

<i>Variable</i>	<i>SS</i>		<i>MS</i>		<i>F</i>	<i>p-value</i>
	<i>Between</i>	<i>Within</i>	<i>Between</i>	<i>Within</i>		
Age	1.043	18.889	.348	.197	1.768	.158
Sex	.020	19.912	.020	.203	.101	.752
Monthly Income	1.244	18.688	.415	.195	2.130	.101
Educational Attainment	2.780	17.152	.927	.179	5.187	.002

Table 10 presents the results of a statistical analysis examining significant differences in farmers' perceptions and experiences of climate change based on their demographic profiles. The analysis considers four variables: age, sex, monthly income, and educational attainment.

For the variable age, the F-value is 1.768 with a p-value of 0.158, indicating no significant differences in perceptions based on age, as the p-value exceeds the commonly accepted threshold of 0.05. Similarly, for sex, the F-value is 0.101 with a p-value of 0.752, confirming that gender does not significantly influence farmers' perceptions of climate change.

Regarding monthly income, the F-value is 2.130 with a p-value of 0.101, suggesting some variation in perceptions based on income. However, this variation is not statistically significant at the 0.05 level. On the other hand, the analysis shows a significant difference for educational attainment, with an F-value of 5.187 and a p-value of 0.002. This indicates that farmers' educational levels significantly affect their perceptions and experiences of climate change. Specifically, those with higher educational attainment tend to have a more informed understanding of climate issues compared to those with lower educational levels. As a result, the null hypothesis for educational attainment is rejected, confirming that there is a significant difference in farmers' perceptions when grouped by their highest level of education.

Overall, the results suggest that demographic factors such as age, sex, and monthly income do not have a significant impact on farmers' perceptions of climate change. However, educational attainment emerges as a critical factor, emphasizing the importance of education

in shaping farmers' awareness and understanding of climate-related challenges. This finding highlights the need for educational programs to enhance farmers' capacity to effectively adapt to climate change.

Conclusions

The study on farmers' perceptions and adaptation strategies to climate change in Kibangay, Lantapan, Bukidnon, revealed key insights into their demographic profile, perceptions, and adaptive responses. The majority of farmers were middle-aged (41% aged 46–60 years), predominantly male (81%), had completed only elementary education, and earned a monthly income of ₱5,000 to ₱15,000. These demographic factors underscored the challenges farmers face in accessing resources and education, which could influence their ability to respond effectively to climate change.

Farmers demonstrated strong awareness of climate change, particularly regarding its effects on rainfall patterns and agricultural productivity. While age, sex, and income did not significantly influence their perceptions, educational attainment emerged as a critical factor. Farmers with higher education levels had a more informed understanding of climate change, highlighting the importance of education in improving awareness and response. The most significant barrier identified was a perceived "lack of technology," though its impact was generally rated as neutral. Crop rotation emerged as the most widely adopted adaptation strategy, with 99% of farmers employing it to mitigate climate impacts.

Based on the findings, the study recommends integrating traditional ecological knowledge with scientific practices through peer-to-peer learning and targeted educational initiatives. Specific policy actions should include the development of farmer training programs focusing on sustainable agricultural practices, the provision of government-funded financial assistance for climate-resilient technologies, and the establishment of community-based agricultural support networks. Local government collaboration is essential in implementing these interventions, particularly through participatory planning, technical support, and infrastructure development.

Additionally, future research should explore longitudinal studies to track changes in farmers' adaptation strategies over time, assess the effectiveness of various interventions, and investigate the socio-economic impacts of climate change on different farming communities. Such studies would contribute to the continuous refinement of policies and programs aimed at enhancing farmers' resilience to climate change.

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